

A STUDY ON CUSTOMERS ATTITUDE TOWARDS E-TAILING IN COIMBATORE

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ABSTRACT

Today , due to improvement in technology and communication , people are attracted towards electronic shopping in order to save time and cost. Online shopping customer behaviour is also called E-shopping customer buying behaviour. E-tailing is known as electronic retailing which is becoming a popular trend nowadays. Online stores are offering almost all sorts of products in their stores even groceries. Online stores are offering best prices, good products and completely hassle-free shopping experiences for the customers. Many online websites are trying to attract a huge number of customers. E-Tailing is nothing but the Electronic Retailing, which was blended together. The success of any E-tailer company in India is depending upon its popularity , its branding image, its unique and fair polices, and its customer relations etc. The purpose of this study is to examine and analyse the attitude and buying behavioural pattern of customers towards online retailing in the study area. Also tried to find out various attitudes of users of Coimbatore city towards the online retailing. The study are is a business town having all classes of people living together and almost all the online stores are have their distribution agencies in the study area. And also the people living in the city use the online shopping websites. The data was collected from 100 respondents. The study result concluded that E-tailing will be having a prosperous growth in the upcoming years.

Key words: E-shopping, E-tailing , online stores and Coimbatore city

Introduction

Online shopping is the process whereby consumers directly buy goods or services from a seller in real time, without an intermediary service, over the internet. It is a form of electronic commerce. In the modern business world, particularly at present time online shopping or E-tailing is the new trend (Transformative Change) of shopping in India, that is used to refer to computer based shopping or E-shopping same like Internet banking or E-banking. Over the past few years, online shopping or E-tailing has increased percentage of online buyers in India. New concept of the online shopping is a great example of the business revolution in India. Online stores are offering best prices , good products and completely hassle-free shopping experience for the customers. Many online websites are trying to attract a huge number of customers. E Tailing is nothing but the Electronic retailing which was blended together. The success of any e-tailer company in India is depending upon its popularity, its branding image, its unique and fair policies, and its customer relations etc. This study aims to identify the respondents perception about online shopping. The study also analyses awareness of consumers towards online shopping. Nature of study is analytical as well as descriptive. In the study both primary and secondary data were used.

Prasanth Singh(2012), stated that online shopping is the new trend. The new online shopping concepts is a great example of the revolution in India. He stated that online shopping has altered in terms of consumers purchasing or buying behaviour and also success of online shopping is based on the popularity, branding image and unique policies.

Koufaris(2002), stated that there is a different factors which come from information systems (Technology acceptance model), marketing (consumer behaviour) and psychology (flow and environmental psychology).

Herms(2000), states that 72 percent of online consumers revealed that customer service are a major factor in online shopping satisfaction.

Hussein(2012), states that financial risks and non delivery risk negatively affect attitude toward online shopping. He also states that domain specific innovatives and subjective norms, attitude towards online shopping positively affect online shopping behaviour.

Statement of Problem

The current study focuses on the customers attitude towards E-tailing in the market. There is a vast growth in the number of internet users nowadays. People were adapting themselves to the emerging technology ; hence internet usage is rapidly increasing. As, there were more number of online retailers in the market people like to purchase things by a single click with the help of mobile applications also. Hence, this study is taken to know the customers attitude towards E-tailing

Scope of the study

This study enables to have clear insight about the customer's attitude towards E-tailing. This study is relevant to the present day's problems and the needs of the public as e-tailing occupy an important position in entertainment, social and political life. An attempt is made to find out the website, which is popular among the existing shopping websites. This study will also help to understand the factors. The study is carried out in Sivakasi Town. The researcher chooses the study area as because almost all the online stores are having their distribution agencies in the study area. And also the people living in the town are using the online shopping websites. The data was collected from 80 respondents. The study result concluded that E-tailing will be having a prosperous growth in the upcoming years. The present study has the following objectives

- To know the socio-economic lifestyle of the users,
- To study the factors that influence the customers to do e-tailing,
- To evaluate the users satisfaction towards e-tailing and
- To suggest measures that help in the improvement of the e-tailers according to the satisfactory level of the users.

Methodology

Both primary and secondary data were collected for the present study. As the study is related to user attitude, the study is mainly based on primary data. The primary data is derived from the views obtained from customers with the help of the questionnaire. The study also depends on the secondary data regarding the history, recent trend and feature of retail shopping in India. The secondary data were further collected from standard text books of related topic, journals, dissertation and thesis. Convenient sampling is adoptable since the

population is unknown. Care has been taken to include all type of customers, with varying income level. In total the researcher has contacted 80 sample informants in Sivakasi Town. The statistical tools used for present analysis, Scaling technique and Weighted average Arithmetic Mean.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

1. Gender wise classification

S.No	Gender	No. Of Respondents	Percentage(%)
1	Male	56	56
2	Female	44	44
Total		100	100

Source: Primary data

It is inferred from the table 1, that most of the respondents are male

2. Age wise classification

S.No.	Age	No. of Respondents	Percentage(%)
1	Below 25 years	39	39
2	25 years -35 years	24	24
3	36 years-45 years	22	22
4	Above 45 years	15	15
Total		100	100

Source: Primary data

It is inferred from the table 2, that most of the respondents come under the age group below 25 years.

3. Occupational status

S.No.	Occupational status	No. of Respondents	Percentage(%)
1	Professional	22	22
2	Entrepreneur	18	18
3	Private employee	13	13
4	Government employee	11	11
5	Students	19	19

6	others	18	18
Total		100	100

Source: Primary data

It is inferred from the table3,that most of the respondents come under the professionals.

4. Influencing factor

S.No.	Influencing factor	No. of Respondents	Percentage(%)
1	Advertisement	54	54
2	Friends and relatives	30	30
3	Flux and banners	7	7
4	Others	9	9
Total		100	100

Source: Primary data

Table 4 shows that majority of the respondents were influenced by the advertisement.

5. Preference of Etailers

S.No.	Applications	No. of Respondents	Percentage(%)
1	Snapdeal	26	26
2	Amazon	11	11
3	Ebay	13	13
4	Filpkart	22	22
5	Shopclues	18	18
6	Others	10	10
Total		100	100

Source: Primary data

Table 5 shows that majority of the respondents use snapdeal

6. Reasons for preference

S.No.	Reason	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
1	Variety of brands	37	37
2	Offers and Discounts	25	25
3	24X7 shopping	13	13
4	Quality	5	5
5	Saves time and cost	20	20
Total		100	100

Source: Primary data

Table 6 shows that majority of the respondents prefer online shopping for the wide choices of brands.

7. Customer satisfaction about usage of applications

S.No.	Applications	HS	S	N	DS	HDS	Total
1	Snapdeal	52	43	4	0	1	100
2	Amazon	36	46	12	4	2	100
3	Ebay	40	54	4	1	1	100
4	Flipkart	65	30	3	0	2	100
5	Shopclues	54	40	2	2	2	100
6	Others	27	43	23	6	1	100

Source: Primary data

8. Ranking the usage of applications

S.No.	Benefits	WAM	Rank
1	Snapdeal	4.50	II
2	Amazon	4.34	IV
3	Ebay	4.19	V
4	Flipkart	4.60	I
5	Shopclues	4.49	III
6	Others	3.96	V

Source :Computed data

From the table 7 and 8 , it is clearly indicated that most of the customers are using the flipkart shopping applications.

FINDINGS

It is inferred from that most of the respondents (56.20%) are male.

It is clear that the majority of the respondents (38.80%) come under the age group below 25 years

It shows that majority of the respondents (22.5%) are professionals.

Present study declares that majority of the respondents (53.8%) were influenced by the advertisement

It shows that majority of the respondents (26.2%) uses snapdeal.

It is clearly indicated that most of the customers are satisfied by the Flipkart.

Most of the respondents prefer online shopping as the wide choices.

SUGGESTION

Companies should have more risk reduction activities as perceived risk could strongly influence customers' online purchase decisions.

Companies should improve customer's value perceptions about the products.

Most of the people feel that products available through online shopping are costly because of the shipping charges whereas in the traditional shopping there are no such charges.

Websites should be made more attractive and appealing to the buyer in order to retain the potential shoppers.

Facilities such as cash on delivery, freeshipping, return policy etc., can be provided to all the products.

CONCLUSIONS

From the above discussion, it is concluded that future of e-tailers in india looking very bright. E-tailers give us the best way to save money and time through purchasing online within the range of budget. Flipkart online store application offering some of the best prices and completely hassle-free shopping experience. The whole concept of online shopping has altered in terms of consumer's purchasing or buying behavior and the success of E-tailers in india is depending upon its popularity, its branding image, and its unique policies.

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